

Adsorption of p-Nitrophenol and Pb (II) ions onto untreated biosorbent prepared from Geranium Plant Waste: Single component adsorption, thermodynamic and kinetic study

Thakare S. S., Pawar R. S., Sonawane K. G., Shinde S. T., Kale A. A.*

PG Dept. of Chemistry and Research Centre, Annasaheb Awate College Manchar (Pune) M.S. India

Correspondence author : Kale A. A.

Received: Jun 18, 2025

Accepted: July 14, 2025

Published: July 15, 2025

Abstract: The capability of untreated biosorbent derived from Geranium Plant Waste (GPW-U) for the adsorption of p-nitrophenol and Lead (II) ions from aqueous solutions was examined. The influence of various experimental parameters, including pH, biosorbent dosage, contact duration, initial concentration and temperature, was analyzed using a batch method. The experimental isotherm data were evaluated through the Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms. The adsorption mechanism was investigated utilizing both the first-pseudo and second-pseudo-order models. Adsorption isotherms at varying temperatures were analyzed to determine thermodynamic parameters such as free energy change, enthalpy change, and entropy change. Thermodynamic studies indicate the feasibility and spontaneity of the adsorption process, as well as its exothermic or endothermic characteristics. The surface area of the biosorbent was calculated using the BET method. Characterization of the biosorbent was performed using XRD, FTIR and FESEM-EDS techniques. This study achieves the adsorption of 86% for P-NP and 83% for Pb (II) ions.

Keywords: Geranium Plant, Lead, Nitrophenol, Isotherm, Kinetic, Thermodynamic.

1. Introduction:

Large volumes and a wide range of chemical wastes and pollutants are being dumped into water resources as a result of the industrial activities that have expanded over the past century. With detrimental impacts on ecosystems (acute and chronic toxicity to aquatic organisms, accumulation in the ecosystems, and loss of habitats and biodiversity due to low biodegradability) and human health (mutagenic and carcinogenic effects), chemical pollution of surface waters poses a threat to the aquatic environment. Numerous synthetic organic compounds, such as phenol and its derivatives, pesticides, aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, dyes, and surfactants, heavy metals are frequently found in trace amounts in water streams, and the presence of high concentrations of toxic pollutants in wastewater has grown to be a significant environmental concern [1, 2].

Phenolic compounds are commonly found in various industrial wastewaters, such as those generated from the production of insecticides, herbicides, dyes, pulp and paper, and other synthetic chemicals. Among these compounds, phenol, as well as nitro- and amino-phenol, are the most prominent in industrial wastewater. These compounds are extensively utilized in the production of explosives, pharmaceuticals, pesticides, pigments, and chemicals used in dye and rubber manufacturing. Due to their toxicity, high environmental mobility, and low biodegradability, the US and European Environmental Protection Agencies have classified these compounds as priority pollutants to be monitored in industrial discharges. Consequently, adsorption technology has emerged as a well-recognized and effective method for water

treatment, with activated carbons being the most commonly utilized adsorbents because of their suitable porous structure and chemical properties [3, 4].

Also water pollution caused by contamination from heavy metals poses serious risks to both environmental and human health. This is due to the tendency of heavy metals to attach themselves to crucial cellular components in living organisms, thereby disrupting their normal functions. Lead (II), the heavy metal we focus on in this study, is frequently found in various ores and is also utilized as a primary raw material in manufacturing batteries and certain alloys. Additionally, the ongoing use of lead compounds as anti-knock agents in petroleum refining contributes to the worsening of lead pollution problems. Given the clear industrial uses of lead compounds, the challenge of lead contamination resulting from the improper release of industrial waste into aquatic environments continues to be a pressing issue. The adverse health effects of Lead (II) have been extensively documented in existing research [5, 6].

Lead (II) is easily absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract, leading to various serious health issues like kidney problems, blood disorders, nervous system complications, and dysfunctions in the reproductive and brain systems. Given the acute toxicity and resistance to biodegradation of Lead (II), addressing its contamination in water is quite difficult. A review of the literature reveals that several approaches have been employed for the removal of aqueous Lead (II), including ion exchange, membrane filtration, chemical precipitation, and electro deposition. However, following the practical applications of these methods, certain associated drawbacks have been identified. These include issues such as the poor thermal stability and regenerability of ion exchange resins, the high maintenance costs of membrane filtration, the significant amount of sludge generated from chemical precipitation, and the substantial energy requirements of electro deposition. In comparison, activated carbon exhibits a significant capacity for metal uptake, rapid adsorption rates, and potential selectivity for different adsorbate [7, 8].

Carbon-based materials with a well-developed internal pore structure are commonly referred to as activated carbon. Numerous carbonaceous rich sources, including wood, coal, lignite, plant waste, industrial waste, agricultural waste, and coconut shell, are used to make AC. AC is a versatile material with many uses in various fields, primarily in the environmental field, thanks to its high surface area, large porosity, well-developed internal pore structure made up of micro-, meso-, and macro-pores, and a wide range of functional groups on its surface [9].

The aim of our work is to investigate untreated Geranium Plant Waste material (GPW-U) for adsorption of lead (II) ion and para nitrophenol under different operating conditions of pH, initial concentration, contact time, adsorbent dose and temperature. In this study, we used the most widely applied isotherm models to evaluate adsorption performance, such as Langmuir and Freundlich. And also the kinetic and thermodynamic studies have been performed to check the order and spontaneity of reaction.

2. Methods and Materials:

Preparation of adsorbate solution: The stock solution of P-NP was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed P-NP in distilled water to make a concentration of 1000 mg/L and Lead (II) ion solution was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed lead nitrate in distilled water to make a concentration of 1 Molar. The experimental solution was obtained by diluting the stock solution in accurate proportions to different initial concentrations.

Preparation of Biosorbent: Rose geranium (*Pelargonium Graveolens* L.) are substantial bushy shrubs located in the vicinity of Narayangaon (India). This plant is also cultivated in various regions of India, China, Algeria, Morocco, France, and Spain. The leaves, flowers, and stems of the plant possess oil-producing trichomes, which yield a fragrant greenish oil. This oil is utilized in the food industry and the medical sector due to its antimicrobial properties. Additionally, it exhibits antifungal and antioxidant activities. The byproduct generated after the oil extraction process is repurposed to create biosorbent materials. Geranium Plant Waste (GPW), collected from the nearby Oil Plant of Narayangaon following oil extraction, was thoroughly washed with copious amounts of hot water and subsequently with distilled water. The waste was then sun-dried for two days. After drying, the material was crushed and placed in an oven at 100°C for one hour, followed by treatment in a muffle furnace at 300°C for three hours. Finally, it was sieved through a mesh with a particle size of 106 microns to obtain powdered biomass, which was utilized for the adsorption study.

Characterization: The specific surface area of GPW-U was determined by gas adsorption using a Quantachrome NOVA TouchWin v1 .2 4 volumetric gas adsorption instrument. The sample was outgassed overnight under nitrogen. Specific surface area was determined with the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation using nitrogen as the adsorbate. The morphology and elemental analysis of GPW-U was measured by FESEM-EDS (Nova NanoSEM NPEP303) before and after adsorption of P-NP and Pb (II) ions onto the surface of GPW-U. The FTIR spectra of GPW-U was characterized by Perkin Elmer Spectrum Version 10.5.3 FTIR spectrophotometer before and after adsorption of P-NP and Pb (II) ions onto the surface of GPW-U. X-ray diffraction data was obtained by a diffractometer MiniFlex (300/600) Benchtop. A batch adsorption study was performed. The concentrations of solutions of p-nitrophenol was measured using UV-VIS Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer and that of lead (II) ions by CHEMITO AA 201 AAS. The pH of the solution was measured by a Systronics 361 pH meter.

Batch Adsorption experiments: At a natural pH of solution, p-nitrophenol (100–300 mg/L) was combined with a GPW-U material (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 g/L). The solutions were maintained at three distinct temperatures of 25, 35, and 45 ± 0.2°C while maintaining a natural pH of the solution in order to assess the impact of temperature. After 110 minutes, the equilibrium was reached. When the equilibration period was over, the mixtures were centrifuged for 30 minutes at 1000 rpm, and the supernatant was filtered through 0.45 µm Whatman filter paper so that the quantity of p-nitrophenol could be measured later. A uv-vis

spectrophotometer set to 430 nm was used to measure the adsorption of p-nitrophenol. The experimental results are the average values of the three trials that were conducted.

GPW-U material (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 g/L) was combined with lead (II) ion solution (100-300 mg/L) at the solution's natural pH. The solutions were maintained at three distinct temperatures of 25, 35, and $45 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ while maintaining a natural pH of the solution in order to assess the impact of temperature. After 120 minutes, the equilibrium was reached. The solutions were centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 30 minutes after the conclusion of the equilibration period, and the supernatant was filtered through 0.45 μm Whatman filter paper for a subsequent measurement of the concentration of Lead (II) ions. AAS was used to measure the adsorption of the lead (II) ion. The experimental results are the average values of the three trials that were conducted. The amount adsorbed by GPW-U was calculated using following formula:

$$q = (C_i - C_e) * \frac{V}{W}$$

The percentage adsorption is calculated using the formula:

$$\% A = \frac{(C_i - C_e)}{C_i} * 100$$

Where q is the amount adsorbed in mg/g, C_i and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentration of experimental solution, V is the volume of experimental solution in liter and W is the weight of biosorbent added in gram.

3. Results and discussion:

BET before adsorption: The surface area of GPW-U at a bath temperature of 77.35K was measured using nitrogen adsorption and the NOVA Quantachrome TouchWin v1.24 device. The study found that the cross-sectional area of a nitrogen molecule is 16.2 Ao^2/mol . The BET-Multipoint method yields a surface area of 3.114 m^2/g for the GPW-U biosorbent. The pore width and pore volume, as measured by the BJH adsorption technique, are 3.39862 nm and 0.00811045 cc/g, respectively.

XRD before adsorption: The MiniFlex (300/600) Benchtop Powder X-ray Diffraction Instrument was used for the XRD study, and Fig. 1 displays the GPW-U adsorbent's results. At 22.52° , high intensity 2θ values are seen. The Scherer equation is used to determine the crystalline size, which falls between 5.27 and 5.96 nm. The amorphous nature of the GPW material is indicated by the sharp peak at $2\theta = 22.52^\circ$. A peak between $20-30^\circ$ 2θ indicated a structure like graphite, which is typical of biochars [10].

Fig. 1: XRD of GPW-U before adsorption

FTIR Analysis: The FTIR spectra of GPW-U taken both before and after the adsorption process are displayed in Fig. 2. Four main peaks were seen at 780 (bending vibration of a C-H bond on the aromatic ring), 1052 (C-O stretching vibrations, specifically within C-O-C bonds), 1317 (C-O stretching vibrations of carboxylate groups) and 1611 (stretching vibrations of C=C bonds in aromatic rings) cm^{-1} prior to the adsorption procedure. The peak at 1317 cm^{-1} vanished after P-NP and Pb (II) ions were adsorbed onto the GPW-U surface. A new peak that was not present in the FTIR spectra of GPW-U prior to adsorption appears at 1704 (C=O stretching vibrations) cm^{-1} after adsorption Pb (II) ion and P-NP. Also after the adsorption of P-NP molecules two new peaks were appeared at 3748 (free O-H group stretching vibration) cm^{-1} and 2931 (C-H stretching vibration) cm^{-1} . Additionally, it was noted that following adsorption, the peaks' width and intensity varied. This implies that functional groups are involved in the adsorption process of P-NP [11] and Pb (II) [12] ions, which occurs on the surface of GPW-U.

Fig. 2: FTIR spectra of GPW-U before and after adsorption

FESEM Analysis: Figure 3 presents FESEM micrographs of GPW-U biosorbent prior to (Fig. 3a) and following the adsorption of P-NP (Fig. 3b) and Pb (II) ions (Fig. 3c). All images were taken at a magnification of 100,000x. The outer surface of the GPW-U biosorbent is characterized by flakes with grooves and cracks, containing some nanometer-sized particles as depicted in Fig. 3a, which contribute to the adsorption process. The changes in surface morphology resulting from the adsorption of Pb (II) ions can be clearly identified by comparing the FESEM micrographs (Fig. 3a & 3c) of the GPW-U and the biomass where Pb (II) ions are bonded, as well as by examining the differences in P-NP adsorption through Fig. 3a & 3b. Alteration took place due to the interaction between Pb (II) ions and P-NP, while the structure of the adsorbed biomass indicates a shift in the average particle size [13, 14].

Fig. 3: SEM images of GPW-U before and after adsorption

EDS Analysis: Figure 4 illustrates the elemental makeup of the samples analyzed through an energy dispersive analysis system. EDS analysis was performed to assess the adsorption of P-NP and Pb (II) ions onto the surface of GPW-U. In Fig. 4a, the presence of carbon is observed, while Fig. 4b highlights oxygen, Fig. 4c shows nitrogen, and Fig. 4d depicts lead. This indicates that new elements (N & Pb) have been introduced to the surface of GPW-U and confirms that adsorption has occurred. The observed changes in the surfaces, as evident from the EDS images before (Fig. 4e) and after the adsorption of P-NP (Fig. 4f) and lead ions (Fig. 4g), also suggest that adsorption has indeed taken place. The table presented in Fig. 4h details the elemental

percentage composition of the samples prior to and following adsorption. EDS spectrum as shown in Fig. 4i confirmed the adsorption [13, 14].

Element	Series	At. %		
		Before Adsorption	After P-NP Adsorption	After Pb ion Adsorption
C	K	77.27	77.92	77.87
O	K	17.80	17.19	16.95
N	K	--	1.43	--
Pb	M	--	--	1.66
Other	K/M	4.93	3.46	3.52

(h) Element Composition Before & After Adsorption

Fig. 4: EDS images of GPW-U before and after adsorption

Effect of pH: The pH levels of solutions containing P-NP and Pb (II) ions were modified to 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 by using 0.1N HCl or NaOH. In each 50 ml solution, 0.05g of GPW-U was introduced at room temperature.

In case of P-NP solution, it was noted that the adsorption of P-NP remained relatively stable at pH levels of 2, 4, and 6, but decreased at pH levels of 8 and 10 (Fig. 5). At elevated pH levels, the abundance of hydroxyl ions competes with P-NP molecules for available adsorption sites, leading to a reduction in adsorption capacity. Therefore, a more acidic environment results in a higher percentage of removal. The impact of pH on adsorption can be understood by examining the ionization level of the adsorbate. In acidic conditions, P-NP exhibits a reduced degree of ionization [15].

For solutions containing Pb (II) ions, precipitation as hydroxide was noticed at pH levels of 8 and 10, leading to a disregard of adsorption capacity at these pH values. The adsorption capacity was observed to rise from 2 to 6, with no significant variation at pH levels of 4 and 6 (Fig. 5). At lower pH levels, hydrogen ions may compete with Pb (II) ions, reducing adsorption; however, as pH rises, the influence of hydrogen ions diminishes, which enhances the adsorption of lead ions [16]. Consequently, an optimum pH of 6 was determined, achieving removal efficiencies of 86% for P-NP and 83% for Pb (II) ions.

Fig. 5: Change in % adsorption with change in pH (Initial conc. = 100 ppm, dose = 0.05 g, vol. = 50 ml, R.T.)

Effect of adsorbent dosage and initial concentration: The impact of the initial concentrations and the adsorbent dosage on the P-NP removal efficiency is depicted in Fig. 6a & b. The study's initial concentrations were 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300 mg/L. Although it is evident that the amount of adsorption rose as the GPW-U dosage rose, an increase in the initial concentration also raised the GPW-U dosage necessary for the removal efficiency to reach its maximum [17]. It is thought that the GPW-U surface include carboxyl, amine and oxygen-containing groups, which can increase the number of adsorption sites for P-NP at the beginning of the process and improve P-NP adsorption onto GPW-U. The overall adsorption rate eventually decreases as the adsorption reaches equilibrium. The findings demonstrated that when the GPW-U dose was increased from 0.01 to 0.05 g/L, the elimination effectiveness of P-NP increases for all tested concentrations.

As the concentration of Pb (II) ions increased from 100 to 300 mg/L, the adsorption rate of GPW-U reduced, as seen in Fig. 6a. The interactions between the adsorbate molecule and the binding zone of the adsorbent surface are responsible for the enhanced adsorption at a lower concentration of the Pb (II) ions. By removing more Pb (II) ions, increasing the adsorbent dosage from 0.01 to 0.05 g/L boosts the adsorption capacity, as seen in Fig. 6b. The increase in the chemical contact area between the adsorbent and the adsorbate was responsible for the highest adsorption [18].

Fig. 6: Change in % adsorption with (a) initial concentration and (b) dose

Effect of contact time: The adsorption pattern illustrates how the contact time affects P-NP adsorption at various initial concentrations. Figure 7 showed that as the adsorption period increased, so did the adsorption of P-NP by GPW-U. After 110 minutes, no discernible increase in adsorption was seen. The amount of P-NP adsorbed stayed nearly constant after that equilibration period. This is because as the contact time increased, more and more P-NP molecules adsorbed onto the GPW-U surface. Additionally, water clusters formed by H-bonds around hydrophilic oxygen-containing groups (like carboxyl, hydroxyl, amino, and phenolic-type groups) caused steric hindrance, which is thought to be effective in preventing P-NP molecules from migrating into the inner pore structures of the GPW-U [19].

By studying the Pb (II) ions uptake over a 120-minute period, the impact of contact duration was ascertained. Within 120 minutes, the percentage removal of Pb (II) ions peaked,

and then there was no discernible change (Fig. 7). The availability of free active sites at the adsorbent surfaces that were progressively occupied over time by metal ions may have contributed to the first period's high removal efficiency. The absorption rate decreased when the binding sites were depleted because metal ions competed for the dwindling number of active sites. Furthermore, it has been observed that a decrease in the boundary layer barrier to mass transfer around the biosorbent particles is the reason for the improvement in removal effectiveness during longer contact times [20].

Fig. 7: Change in % adsorption with change in time (Initial conc. = 100 ppm, dose = 0.05 g, vol. = 50 ml, pH = 6, R.T.)

Effect of temperature: The adsorption process is significantly impacted by temperature. According to Fig. 8, the percentage removal of adsorbate, namely para-nitrophenol and Lead (II) ions, increases with increasing temperature. This is due to the fact that raising the temperature will accelerate the pace at which the adsorbate molecules diffuse through the GPW-U adsorbent particle's interior pores and across the external boundary layer [21, 22].

Fig. 7: Change in % adsorption with temperature of solution (Initial conc. = 100 ppm, Dose = 0.05 g, pH = 6, vol. = 50 ml)

Adsorption isotherms: Finding the best correlation between the equilibrium curves is crucial for optimizing the design of an adsorption system for the adsorption of adsorbate. Monolayers with uniform, finite adsorption sites are the basis for Langmuir adsorption isotherms. Thus, no further adsorption takes place after the saturation value is attained. Additionally, interactions between molecules adsorbed on nearby molecular sites are believed to be absent. The Freundlich Isotherm refers to a physical kind of adsorption where the bonds are weak and the adsorption takes place in several layers.

Langmuir Adsorption Isotherm is calculated using: $\frac{C_e}{Q_e} = \frac{C_e}{Q_m} + \frac{1}{Q_m K_L}$

Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm is calculated using: $\ln Q_e = \ln K_F + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e$

Where, C_e is equilibrium concentration of the said adsorbate, Q_e is adsorption capacity that gets adsorbed at equilibrium, Q_m is maximum adsorption capacity, n is the value indicating the degree of linearity between the adsorbate solution and the adsorption process K_L & K_F Langmuir & Freundlich Adsorption Constant respectively.

Fig. 8: Adsorption Isotherms (Initial conc. = 100 ppm, Dose = 0.05 g, pH = 6, vol. = 50 ml)

The R^2 values obtained from the graph for P-NP concerning the Langmuir adsorption isotherm [Fig. 8a] is 0.9869, whereas for the Freundlich adsorption isotherm [Fig. 8b], it is 0.9979. Regarding the adsorption of Pb (II) ions, the R^2 values are 0.9884 and 0.9989, respectively. These R^2 values suggest that the adsorption processes for both P-NP and Pb (II) ions conform to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. It is also noted that adsorption can take place in multiple layers on the GPW-U surface [23, 24].

Adsorption kinetics: In the batch adsorption process, kinetic studies yield insights into optimal conditions, the mechanism of sorption, and potential rate-controlling steps. To achieve this, pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order kinetics are utilized on the adsorption data.

The pseudo-first-order-kinetic model is given as: $\ln(Q_e - Q_t) = \ln Q_e - k_1 t$

The pseudo-second-order-kinetic model is given as: $\frac{t}{Q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 Q_e^2} + \frac{t}{Q_e}$

Q_t is the amount adsorbed at time t , Q_e is the equilibrium amount, t is time in min, and k_1 & k_2 are the rate constants.

Fig. 9: Kinetic Adsorption data (Initial conc. = 100 ppm, Dose = 0.05 g, pH = 6, vol. = 50 ml)

The R^2 values derived from the graph for P-NP in relation to the pseudo-first-order kinetic model [Fig. 9a] is 0.9111, while for the pseudo-second-order kinetic model [Fig. 9b], it is 0.9254. In the case of Pb (II) ions adsorption, the R^2 values are 0.9612 and 0.9280, respectively. From these R^2 values, it can be inferred that the adsorption process of P-NP adheres to the pseudo-second-order kinetic model, whereas the adsorption of Pb (II) ions aligns with the pseudo-first-order kinetic model. Therefore, for P-NP adsorption, the rate of adsorption is directly proportional to the concentration of p-nitrophenol, whereas for Pb (II) ions adsorption, the rate does not exhibit a direct proportionality to the concentration of Lead (II) ions [25, 26].

Thermodynamics studies: Thermodynamic calculations regarding the adsorption process are essential to determine if the process is spontaneous. Such thermodynamic studies indicate the feasibility and spontaneity of the adsorption process, as well as its exothermic or endothermic characteristics. The Van't Hoff equation was employed to ascertain the thermodynamic parameters. The temperature dependence of adsorption process is associated with changes in several thermodynamic parameters such as standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) of adsorption. The calculations were done by using the following equation:

$$\ln K = -\left(\frac{\Delta G^\circ}{RT}\right) = -\left(\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT}\right) + \left(\frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R}\right)$$

Fig. 10: Plot of $\ln K$ vs. $1/T$ for adsorption on GPW-U. (Initial conc. = 100 ppm, Dose = 0.05 g, pH = 6, vol. = 50 ml)

The Van't Hoff plot's slope and intercept (Fig. 10) were used to calculate the values of ΔH° and ΔS° . The values of ΔH° and ΔS° for p-nitrophenol were 9.923 and 0.048 kJ/mol whereas those for lead (II) ions were 6.631 and 0.035 kJ/mol. In general, physisorption has a change of standard free energy (ΔG°) between -20 and 0 kJ/mol, while chemisorption has a range of -80 to -400 kJ/mol. At the temperature range under investigation, the total ΔG° of the adsorbent is negative, ranging from -4.5 to 5.5 kJ/mol for P-NP and -4 to 4.7 kJ/mol for Pb (II) ions. These findings support a spontaneous physical adsorption of lead (II) ions and p-nitrophenol, suggesting that this system does not obtain energy from outside sources [27, 28].

Conclusion:

This study investigated the equilibrium and dynamic adsorption of p-nitrophenol and lead (II) ions onto GPW-U under various operational parameters, including initial concentration, contact time, adsorbent dosage, solution pH, and temperature. The highest adsorption capacity was observed with the addition of 0.05 g/L of GPW-U at a pH of 6 for 100 ppm concentration. The findings indicated that the adsorption of p-nitrophenol and lead (II) ions onto GPW-U diminished as pH increased, while it enhanced with rising temperature. The equilibrium adsorption isotherm for both adsorbate conformed to the Freundlich isotherm model. Kinetic studies revealed that the adsorption profiles of the adsorbent adhered to a pseudo-second-order kinetic model for P-NP adsorption and a pseudo-first-order kinetic model for Pb (II) ions adsorption. The results demonstrated that the adsorption of both adsorbate onto GPW-U was a physisorption process, which is more favorable at elevated temperatures. It was discovered that the presence of water facilitates the formation of water clusters that are adsorbed onto the GPW-U surface through hydrogen bonding with hydrophilic oxygen-containing groups, particularly carboxyl, carbonyl and hydroxyl groups. In light of these findings, we propose that hydrogen bonding, electron donor-acceptor interactions, and Lewis acid/base interactions are the primary mechanisms affecting the adsorption capacity.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this articles.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

All the authors contributed equally to analyzing the data and in writing this manuscript.

References:

- [1] Dhorabe, Prashant T., Dilip H. Lataye, and Ramakant S. Ingole. "Adsorptive removal of 4-nitrophenol from aqueous solution by activated carbon prepared from waste orange peels." *Journal of Hazardous, Toxic, and Radioactive Waste* 21.2 (2017): 04016015.
- [2] Nwosu, F. O., F. A. Adekola, and A. O. Salami. "Adsorption of 4-Nitrophenol using pilli nut shell active carbon." *Pakistan Journal of Analytical & Environmental Chemistry* 18.1 (2017): 69-83.
- [3] Altaher, Hossam, and Andrea M. Dietrich. "Characterizing o-and p-nitrophenols adsorption onto innovative activated carbon prepared from date pits." *Water science and technology* 69.1 (2014): 31-37.
- [4] Popovici, Daniela Roxana, et al. "Adsorption of p-nitrophenol onto activated carbon prepared from fir sawdust: isotherm studies and error analysis." *Reaction Kinetics, Mechanisms and Catalysis* 133.1 (2021): 483-500.
- [5] Zhang, Zhen, et al. "Adsorption of Pb (II) and Cd (II) by magnetic activated carbon and its mechanism." *Science of the Total Environment* 757 (2021): 143910.
- [6] Hamid, Abdul, et al. "The Influence of NaOH Activator Concentration on the Synthesis of Activated Carbon from Banana Peel for Pb (II) Adsorption." *EKSAKTA: Berkala Ilmiah Bidang MIPA* 23.03 (2022): 158-166.
- [7] Basu, Mousumi, Arun K. Guha, and Lalitagauri Ray. "Adsorption of lead on cucumber peel." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 151 (2017): 603-615.
- [8] Natrayan, L., et al. "Development and characterization of carbon-based adsorbents derived from agricultural wastes and their effectiveness in adsorption of heavy metals in waste water." *Bioinorganic Chemistry and Applications* 2022.1 (2022): 1659855.
- [9] Bhatnagar, Amit, et al. "An overview of the modification methods of activated carbon for its water treatment applications." *Chemical Engineering Journal* 219 (2013): 499-511.

- [10] Lee, Sang-Min, Sang-Hye Lee, and Jae-Seung Roh. "Analysis of activation process of carbon black based on structural parameters obtained by XRD analysis." *Crystals* 11.2 (2021): 153.
- [11] Dhorabe, Prashant T., Dilip H. Lataye, and Ramakant S. Ingole. "Removal of 4-nitrophenol from aqueous solution by adsorption onto activated carbon prepared from *Acacia glauca* sawdust." *Water science and technology* 73.4 (2016): 955-966.
- [12] Divahar, R., et al. "Lemon peel activated carbon: a sustainable solution for lead ion removal from E-waste bioleachate." *Sustainable Chemistry for the Environment* 6 (2024): 100094.
- [13] Yadav, Nidhi, et al. "Adsorption and equilibrium studies of phenol and para-nitrophenol by magnetic activated carbon synthesised from cauliflower waste." *Environmental Engineering Research* 25.5 (2020): 742-752.
- [14] Ganiyu Abimbola Adebisi, Ganiyu Abimbola Adebisi, Zaira Zaman Chowdhury Zaira Zaman Chowdhury, and P. A. Alaba. "Equilibrium, kinetic, and thermodynamic studies of lead ion and zinc ion adsorption from aqueous solution onto activated carbon prepared from palm oil mill effluent." (2017): 958-968.
- [15] Abd-Hadi, Ghufuran Muafaq, and Sami D. Salman. "Adsorption of para nitro-phenol by activated carbon produced from alhagi." *Sains Malaysiana* 49.1 (2020): 57-67.
- [16] Deng, Zhihua, et al. "Modification of coconut shell-based activated carbon and purification of wastewater." *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials* 4.1 (2021): 65-73.
- [17] Liu, Lanqi, Guozhi Deng, and Xianyang Shi. "Adsorption characteristics and mechanism of p-nitrophenol by pine sawdust biochar samples produced at different pyrolysis temperatures." *Scientific Reports* 10.1 (2020): 5149.
- [18] Dehghani, Mohammad Hadi, et al. "Removal of toxic lead from aqueous solution using a low-cost adsorbent." *Scientific reports* 13.1 (2023): 3278.
- [19] Elhleli, Hanedi, et al. "Biocarbon Derived from *Opuntia ficus indica* for p-Nitrophenol Retention." *Processes* 8.10 (2020): 1242.
- [20] Asrat, Yosef, et al. "Adsorption Phenomenon of *Arundinaria alpina* Stem-Based Activated Carbon for the Removal of Lead from Aqueous Solution." *Journal of Chemistry* 2021.1 (2021): 5554353.
- [21] Eldemerdash, Usama Nour, Taha Ebrahiem Farrag, and Sherien AbdElkader. "Modified Activated Carbon for Adsorptive Removal of Para-Nitrophenol from Industrial Wastewater (IWW)." *Port-Said Engineering Research Journal* 27.1 (2023): 1-7.
- [22] Natrayan, L., et al. "Development and characterization of carbon-based adsorbents derived from agricultural wastes and their effectiveness in adsorption of heavy metals in waste water." *Bioinorganic Chemistry and Applications* 2022.1 (2022): 1659855.

- [23] Simiyu, Lydiah N., et al. "Kinetic modelling of p-Nitrophenol ions adsorption onto activated and non-activated carbon from macadamia nutshells in a model solution." (2023).
- [24] Kavand, Mohammad, Parisa Eslami, and Laleh Razeh. "The adsorption of cadmium and lead ions from the synthesis wastewater with the activated carbon: Optimization of the single and binary systems." *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 34 (2020): 101151.
- [25] Wasilewska, Malgorzata, et al. "Nitrophenols removal from aqueous solutions by activated carbon—temperature effect of adsorption kinetics and equilibrium." *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 9.4 (2021): 105459.
- [26] Thabede, Patience Mapule, Ntaote David Shooto, and Eliazer Bobby Naidoo. "Removal of methylene blue dye and lead ions from aqueous solution using activated carbon from black cumin seeds." *South African Journal of chemical engineering* 33.1 (2020): 39-50.
- [27] Gabr, Sahar Saad, et al. "Linear and nonlinear regression analysis of phenol and P-nitrophenol adsorption on a hybrid nanocarbon of ACTF: kinetics, isotherm, and thermodynamic modeling." *Applied Water Science* 13.12 (2023): 230.
- [28] Abd El-wahaab, Badr, et al. "Adsorption of lead (Pb (II)) from contaminated water onto activated carbon: kinetics, isotherms, thermodynamics, and modeling by artificial intelligence." *Sustainability* 17.5 (2025): 2131.